

Estimation and evaluation of the effects of future implementation of GPS-based bus priority in Copenhagen

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Background

“ TRANSPORT INITIATIVE 2 (Copenhagen Climate Plan): Public transport gets even better – we invest in **comfort, reliability, minimal travel times** and **smooth linkages** between the different public transportation systems. [...] ”

MORE ATTRACTIVE PUBLIC TRANSPORT

The road space utilization can be optimized considerably if the same amount of passengers are transported by bus instead of by car.

The project idea

INTELLIGENT TRANSPORT SYSTEMS
The application of **information and communication technology** to vehicles and **transport infrastructure**.

“ TRANSPORT INITIATIVE 10 (Copenhagen Climate Plan): Intelligent transport systems **optimise** the city's **traffic signals** to the benefit of **bicyclists and busses** [...] ”

Description of the system

Buses are equipped with a **GPS receiver**, which continuously gets its location from GPS satellites. When the location coordinates correspond to predefined detection points (“**virtual detectors**”), placed at a certain distance before the traffic signal, a **priority request** is sent – usually via radio – to the traffic signal controller.

Priority can be given:

- by **green extension**, if the bus approaches the signal during the green phase;
- by **green recall**, if the bus approaches the signal during the red phase;
- by inserting an **extra stage** in the signal plan.

Advantages

- Low installation and maintenance cost
- Rapidity of implementation
- Easiness to extend the system
- Flexibility in the relocation of detectors
- Possibility of implementing differential priority
- Great potential to integrate the system with real-time traffic information.

Benefits

- Shorter travel times
- Higher punctuality and reliability
- Operational savings

➔ **Potential for MODAL SHIFT !**

BUS PRIORITY

Different measures to **prioritize** buses in the network, both on the links (roads) and at the nodes (intersections), with the purpose of relieving buses from congestion and thus achieving **shorter travel times** and **higher punctuality**.

Examples of bus priority

Example of GPS-based bus priority at traffic signals from London

Application of the project idea

Simulation model of the network around Flintholm station (2018)

Evaluation parameters

The project is in progress. Therefore, no results are currently available.

References

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